

Synthesis and Physiological Activity of 2*H*-[1]-Benzothiopyrano[3,4-*e*][1,3]oxazine-5-ones

B. SUCHARITA REDDY and MALLESHWAR DARBARWAR*

Department of Chemistry, Osmania University, Hyderabad-500 007

Manuscript received 5 August 1985, accepted 24 December 1985

Fourteen benzothiopyranooxazine-5-ones have been synthesised by the condensation of 4-hydroxy-1-thiocoumarin and 6-chloro-4-hydroxy-1-thiocoumarin with different Schiff bases (derived from aromatic aldehydes and aniline) in acetic acid medium. The possible reaction mechanism has been advanced. Analytical, spectral and physiological properties of the compounds have been evaluated.

1-Thiocoumarins are known to exhibit varied physiological properties, namely anticoagulant, anti-allergic, bactericidal and insecticidal activities. Oxazines are reported to act as antibiotic, amoebicidal, anaesthetic and antitubercular agents¹. During search for compounds of better activity it was considered worthwhile to synthesise thiocoumarins with fused oxazine ring and evaluate their physiological properties. It was with this view that the following work has been undertaken. The present communication, therefore, deals with synthesis of a new heterocyclic system, viz. 2*H*-benzothiopyrano[3,4-*e*][1,3]oxazine-5-one.

As a representative case, 4-hydroxy-1-thiocoumarin (1)^{1,2} was treated with two moles of Schiff base (2) (obtained from *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde and aniline) in acetic acid at room temperature. The contents were shaken well and a clear dark brown solution was obtained with the evolution of heat. This solution on stirring for ten minutes yielded a yellow compound 3 (m.p. 256°; single spot on tlc, benzene-ethyl acetate, 1:1). The compound was not soluble in sodium bicarbonate solution indicating that hydroxyl group at 4-position in 1-thiocoumarin was not free and involved in the reaction. Elemental analysis indicated presence of nitrogen and sulphur (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

Its spectra of the compound showed absorptions at 1640 (CO of thiocoumarin) and 1230 cm^{-1} (C—O—C). The absorptions due to OH group of 4-hydroxy-1-thiocoumarin and that due to NH (Schiff base) were absent. In uv spectra, absorption maxima at 232 ($\log \epsilon$ 4.80, Ph—S chromophore) and 316 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.2; cinnamoyl chromophore) were present. Pmr spectra in TFA and CDCl_3 indicated signals at δ 6.2 (1H, s, NCH(Ph)O) and 8.1 (1H, s, CCH(Ph)N) and a multiplet at δ 6.8-8.0 (17H, Ar). In addition, another pmr spectra of the compound (in TFA and CDCl_3) obtained by the reaction of 4-hydroxythiocoumarin with Schiff base (obtained from *p*-tolualdehyde and aniline) was also recorded to have an internal standard. In this spectrum, a new signal at δ 1.8 (6H, s, CH_3) was observed in addition to all signals mentioned above.

On the basis of above chemical and spectral data the structure of the compound has been assigned as 2*H*-benzothiopyrano[3,4-*e*][1,3]oxazine-5-one (3). The compound showed characteristic fragmentation pattern in the mass spectra. The peak (M^+) was not observed in the spectra indicating that the molecule was highly unstable under the conditions. However, the M^+ split by RDA process and as a result two fragments appeared at m/z 300 (10%) and 215 (25%). The latter ion correspond to a molecule of Schiff base. The second RDA process was followed after the ion m/z 300 lost CO to give rise to two ions at m/z 136. The ion m/z 215 lost a proton to form m/z 214 which on subsequent cleavage may give rise m/z 137 and 77 or may fragment to form m/z 111. The ion m/z 137 constituted the base peak in the mass spectrum. The possible structures of these ions and mass spectral fragmentation pattern is shown in Scheme 2.

Mechanism: 4-Hydroxy-1-thiocoumarin is acidic and reacts with one molecule of protonated Schiff base to form 4. The Schiff base are known

Scheme 2

ot act as proton acceptors and also act as potential source of aldehyde in heterocyclisation reactions. Hanmanthu and Ratnam⁸ reported the formation of 1,3-naphthoxazines by the reaction of Schiff bases with α -naphthol and β -naphthol. 4-Hydroxycoumarin reacts similarly with Schiff bases forming coumarinooxazines⁴. The intermediate 4 further reacts with aldehyde to form 5 which cyclises by loss of a molecule of water to 3 (Scheme 3).

Adopting the above procedure thirteen benzo-thioipyranooxazines have been prepared by condensation of each simple and 6-chloro-4-hydroxy-1-thiocoumarins with Schiff bases obtained from aniline and different aldehydes, namely benzaldehyde, *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde, *p*-methylbenzal-

dehyde 2,4-dichlorobenzaldehyde, *p*-anisaldehyde, furfural and pyridine-3-aldehyde. Their m.p.'s, analytical and spectral data are presented in Table 1.

Scheme 3

Physiological activity : All the compounds have been screened for antibacterial (tube-dilution method) activity against two bacteria, namely *Bacillus subtilis* (gram +ve) and *Escherichia coli* (gram -ve) and antifungal activity (plate method) against two fungi, namely *Aspergillus niger* and *Alternaria alternata*. Among the compounds tested most active were 9-chloro-3-*N*-phenyl-2,4-di(*p*-chlorophenyl)benzothioipyranooxazine-5-one, 9-chloro-3-*N*-phenyl-2,4-di-(2',5'-dichlorophenyl)benzothioipyranooxazine-5-one, 3-*N*-phenyl-2,4-di(2',4'-dichlorophenyl)benzothioipyranooxazine-5-one and 3-*N*-phenyl-2,4 di(*p*-chlorophenyl)benzothioipyranooxazine 5-one against both *B. subtilis* and *E. coli* at 10 ppm.

9-Chloro-2,4-di(2',4'-dichlorophenyl)-3-*N*-phenylbenzothioipyranooxazine-5-one and 2,4-di(2',4'-d-

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF 2H-BENZOTHIOPYRANO[3,4-*b*] [1,3-*e*]OXAZINE-5-ONES (3)*

Sl. no.	R	Ar	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			λ_{max} (log ϵ) nm	ν_{max} cm ⁻¹
						C	H	N		
1.	-	C ₆ H ₅	218	67	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ O ₂ NS	77.80 (77.85)	4.63 (4.7)	3.10 (3.13)	233 (4.8) 318 (4.1)	1 635 1 230
2.	-	<i>p</i> -Cl-C ₆ H ₄	256	62	C ₂₀ H ₁₀ O ₂ NSCl ₂	67.57 (67.59)	3.62 (3.69)	2.66 (2.71)	238 (4.4) 324 (3.8)	1 640 1 230
3.	-	<i>p</i> -H ₃ C-C ₆ H ₄	168	68	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ O ₂ NS	78.26 (78.31)	5.20 (5.26)	2.90 (2.94)	235 (4.5) 329 (4.7)	1 640 1 232
4.	-	2,4-Cl ₂ -C ₆ H ₃	165	62	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ O ₂ NSCl ₂	59.62 (59.69)	2.85 (2.91)	2.36 (2.40)	237 (4.4) 321 (4.5)	1 640 1 230
5.	-	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	100	67	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₂ NS	73.30 (73.73)	4.88 (4.93)	2.70 (2.76)	231 (4.7) 329 (3.9)	1 635 1 232
6.	-	Furfuryl	146	66	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ O ₄ NS	70.20 (70.25)	3.92 (3.98)	3.20 (3.27)	239 (4.2) 325 (3.6)	1 640 1 230
7.	-	3-Pyridyl	175	63	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ S	72.10 (72.76)	4.18 (4.23)	9.30 (9.35)	231 (3.7) 331 (3.9)	1 635 1 232
8.	9-Chloro	C ₆ H ₅	220	67	C ₂₀ H ₁₀ O ₂ NSCl	72.30 (72.34)	4.10 (4.15)	2.85 (2.91)	238 (4.3) 329 (3.6)	1 635 1 230
9.	9-Chloro	<i>p</i> -Cl-C ₆ H ₄	120	67	C ₂₀ H ₁₀ O ₂ NSCl ₂	63.32 (63.38)	3.25 (3.27)	2.50 (2.55)	237 (4.4) 320 (4.5)	1 640 1 230
10.	9-Chloro	<i>p</i> -H ₃ C-C ₆ H ₄	178	67	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ O ₂ NSCl	73.0 (73.08)	4.36 (4.71)	2.70 (2.75)	231 (4.6) 313 (4.0)	1 650 1 235
11.	9-Chloro	2,4-Cl ₂ -C ₆ H ₃	192	65	C ₂₀ H ₁₀ O ₂ NSCl ₂	56.36 (56.40)	2.52 (2.59)	2.20 (2.26)	237 (4.4) 320 (4.5)	1 640 1 230
12.	9-Chloro	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	236	67	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₂ NSCl	68.70 (68.70)	4.37 (4.43)	2.52 (2.58)	-	1 635 1 235
13.	9-Chloro	Furfuryl	180	65	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ O ₄ NSCl	65.00 (65.07)	3.40 (3.47)	3.00 (3.03)	238 (4.2) 331 (3.9)	1 635 1 230
14.	9-Chloro	3-Pyridyl	238	62	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₂ SCl	71.80 (71.84)	3.92 (3.99)	9.27 (9.31)	238 (3.9) 332 (3.9)	1 640 1 230

*Solvent of recrystallisation : acetic acid.

chlorophenyl)-3-*N*-phenylbenzothiopyrano-oxazine-*f*-one have shown an inhibition of 50% against *A. niger* and *A. alternata* at 100 ppm only.

The testing results indicate that a halogen when present in thiocoumarin ring or present in *N*-phenyl moiety enhances the activity and which is maximum when halogens are present in both the places.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Uv spectra were recorded in methanol on a Beckman DB spectrophotometer, ir spectra (KBr) on a Perkin-Elmer 337 spectrophotometer, pmr spectra (TFA and CDCl₃) on a Varian A-60 D spectrometer (TMS as internal standard) and mass spectra on a Perkin-Elmer-Hitachi-RMU-6L double focussing instrument operating at 70 eV using direct inlet system. Tlc analysis was performed on glass plates (10×5 cm²) coated (250 mμ) with silica gel G (containing 13% calcium sulphate as binder).

General procedure :

2H-Benzothiopyrano[3,4-*e*][1,3]oxazine-5-one (3) : 4-Hydroxy-1-thiocoumarin (0.9 g) and Schiff

base (obtained from *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde and aniline ; 2.1 g) were mixed in acetic acid and shaken well. The resulting dark brown solution was stirred at 30° for 1 h. A yellow compound that separated was filtered and recrystallised from acetic acid in the form of light yellow needles (1.8 g, 62%), m. p. 256° (Found : C, 67.57 ; H, 3.62 ; N, 2.66. C₂₀H₁₉O₂NSCl₂ requires : C, 67.57 ; H, 3.68 ; N, 2.71)%.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (B.S) expresses thanks to U. G. C., New Delhi, for the award of Teacher Fellowship (F. I. P.). Thanks are also due to Prof. C. Manoharachary for evaluating the physiological activity.

References

1. E. ZIEGLER and H. JUNEK, *Monatsh. Chem.*, 1955, 86, 37.
2. P. S. JAMKHANDI and S. RAJGOPAL, *Arch. Pharm. (Weinheim. Ger.)*, 1967, 300, 561.
3. P. HANMANATHU and C. V. RATNAM, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1977, 15, 1019.
4. S. Y. DITHA and J. R. MERCHANT, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1978, 38, 3607.